

1 **Participatory analysis of Sustainable Land and Water Management Practices for**
2 **integrated rural development in Myanmar**

3 Short title: Participatory Sustainable Land and Water Management analysis for rural Myanmar

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28 **ABSTRACT**

29 Besides providing reliable water resources for agricultural production, rural development efforts in
30 Myanmar should target rural water security in terms of safe water supply and sanitation, and by mitigating
31 water-related hazards. However, very few studies are available over the status of water-related
32 development in rural areas of country, and consequently on suitable practical solutions. The present
33 paper describes a participatory workshop undertaken involving 45 rural development officers of the
34 Department of Rural Development (DRD) of the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Irrigation (MOALI),
35 aimed at identifying suitable Sustainable Land and Water Management (SLWM) practices to be developed
36 in rural areas of the country. Adoption of Water Safety Plans (WSP), water harvesting, and soil and water
37 bioengineering were strongly supported, while the need of improving water sanitation, especially in
38 poorest areas, was made evident. Insights of the participatory process confirmed that the poorest regions
39 of Myanmar have also the worst water management structures. The results of the present work can
40 represent a baseline information and a needs assessment for future development projects in the country.
41 However, there is a strong need of more studies and reports targeting marginalized rural contexts of
42 Myanmar, to support an equitable development.

43 **Keywords:** erosion, experts participation, public engagement, soil and water bioengineering, water
44 harvesting, Water Safety Plans.

45

46 **Introduction**

47 Myanmar is rich in natural resources that can support human development and environmental health
48 (World Bank, 2019a). Water resources are abundant, but unevenly distributed due to variation in time
49 (with the 80% of rain falling in the rainy season) and space (FAO, 2016; Taft & Evers, 2016). The country is
50 yet undergoing a rapid political change: it was ruled by a military junta for three decades, until free
51 elections of 2015 (World Bank, 2019a). In this situation, the establishment of effective Integrated Water
52 Resources Management (IWRM) it is vital for the development of the country (Foran *et al.*, 2019), and
53 especially in rural areas, which accounts for the 70% of total population (UNFPA, 2014). In this framework,
54 according to the “National Strategy for Rural Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene” (UNICEF, 2016) some
55 unsolved key issues in rural areas include the need for increasing water sanitation technologies for poorer
56 households and in remote areas; management issues related to environmental impacts of water uses; and
57 the structural weakness of monitoring and management information systems related to the water sector.
58 These issues can be related to IWRM, since this approach claims for the integration of multiple uses of
59 water, including environment, and is also requesting the integration of data and approaches. The recent
60 National Water Policy (National Water Resources Committee (NWRC), 2015) is further stressing an IWRM
61 approach to water supply and sanitation, with a specific focus in rural areas, recognizing also the need of
62 adequate capacity building and the setting up of adequate database and information systems.

63 However, while, especially at the level of small rural settlements, water management issues are
64 jeopardizing population's health and livelihoods, the water resources development focus in the country is
65 still linked with large infrastructure development, aiming at tackling country-scale challenges (Foran *et al.*,
66 2019; Taft & Evers, 2016). On the other hand, in the latest years, UNESCO and UN Water stressed the
67 importance to reach also the day-to-day realities of vulnerable groups and small communities with
68 adequate water resources planning and management, as stated in 2019 World Water Development Report
69 "Leaving no one behind" (WWAP (UNESCO World Water Assessment Programme), 2019). In coordination
70 with large infrastructures, small-scale water development efforts are then needed to secure the results of
71 SDG 6, at the global scale as well as in Myanmar. Along with freshwater management issues, erosion and
72 land degradation represent a major threat to rural livelihoods in the country, also considering that
73 Myanmar has the highest erosion hazard of South Asia (Htwe *et al.*, 2015).

74 In the framework of water resources development, especially within international cooperation projects and
75 in rural development actions localized in small areas, the involvement of local stakeholders has proven to
76 be fundamental to ensure good project outcomes, for the implementation of sustainable technological
77 solutions, and for reducing inequalities (Alfredo *et al.*, 2016; Castelli *et al.*, 2018). However, if on the one
78 hand well addressed stakeholders' participation can provide the identification of general basics needs, on
79 the other, expert participation has been proven to be also fundamental. The latter is particularly useful for
80 balancing population needs with feasible solutions, as well as for choosing technological options that local
81 authorities can really manage even after the completion of international development projects (van Ast &
82 Gerrits, 2016).

83 This paper presents the results of a participatory process aiming at selecting Sustainable Land and Water
84 Management (SLWM) practices for integrated rural development in Myanmar. The process was realized in
85 two days, involving rural development officers of Myanmar Department of Rural Development (DRD),
86 falling under the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Irrigation (MOALI), devoted to the implementation
87 of water access and sanitation in rural areas. The aim of this research work is then to present some useful
88 options for small-scale rural land and water development in the country, focusing on rural water access and
89 sanitation, and on water- and land-related hazards that threaten the environmental health of rural
90 settlements (e.g. erosion, landslides and pollution). Issues related to water for food production were
91 purposely not considered in order to have a narrower focus on the above-mentioned subjects and since a
92 large body of literature is present over the topic for Myanmar (Matsuno *et al.*, 2013; Rowell & Soe, 2015;
93 Than, 2018). Moreover, according to Myanmar administrative structure, the responsibilities of irrigation
94 management are not held by DRD, but by the so-called Irrigation and Water Utilization Management
95 Department. Given this premise the present participatory process focuses DRD topics of interest.

96 The scale of the present work is limited to the participatory process undertaken, but very few literature
97 papers or studies have addressed possible small-scale water development options in Myanmar. Therefore,
98 the paper can represent a baseline assessment useful for decision making on investments in both future
99 development cooperation projects and national development plans. The work provides an initial needs
100 assessment and some suggestions regarding sustainable and feasible technical solutions for SLWM in
101 Myanmar. Moreover, the methodology presented can be replicated in many similar contexts, providing a
102 standard approach for a rapid - but still informed- assessment of water development needs in marginalized
103 rural areas. Results can be considered for matching the objectives set by SDGs 6 "Clean Water and
104 Sanitation", 11 "Sustainable Cities and Communities", and 15 "Life on Land".

105 **Myanmar water resources and rural development context**

106 Myanmar (Republic of Union of Myanmar) is located in South East Asia, approximately from 9°55'-28°15'N
107 and 92°10'-101°11' E, with a maximum north–south extent of about 2500 km and a maximum west–east
108 extent of about 900 km. The country has mountains ranges in the north and in the west, while it is
109 dominated by alluvial floodplains in the center. It is divided in 22 sub-national administrations including
110 States, Regions, Union Territories, Self-Administered Zones and Self-Administered Divisions. The capital is
111 Naypyidaw.

112 The major rivers of the country are the Ayeyarwady (Irrawaddy), the Salween, the Chindwin and the
113 Sittaung, where the first one is by far the largest and the most important one for the country, with about
114 2170 km of length. At the same time, part of the country relies on groundwater resources (some of them of
115 alluvial origin) which are often affected by contamination issues and at risk of depletion, due to increasing
116 water demand (Pavelic *et al.*, 2015). The monsoon season starts around the end of May and the beginning
117 of June, lasting to September (Sen Roy & Kaur, 2000). The annual rainfall amount has a great variation,
118 ranging from 500-1000 mm in the central dry zone, to 4000-6000 mm in the western coast (FAO, 2016).
119 Rainy season diurnal temperature can vary from 21 to 34°C, while they drop to 11 to 23°C in the cold
120 season (Taft & Evers, 2016). The country is still one of the most affected by climatic hazards, including
121 floods, cyclones and droughts (Kreft & Eckstein, 2014).

122 According to the Myanmar Living Conditions Survey 2017 (Central Statistical Organization of the Ministry of
123 Planning and Finance *et al.*, 2017), water access in rural areas improved since 2015, firstly thanks to the
124 private sector investment, and then with an increasing effort of DRD and its partner which have
125 implemented around 5000 water supply facilities per year around Myanmar. In these areas, many
126 households must transport water from the source to the consumption point, increasing the risk of
127 contamination by the use of dirty containers and storage systems. The worst situation in terms of access to
128 improved water sources is in Rakhine State (Central Statistical Organization of the Ministry of Planning and
129 Finance *et al.*, 2017). According to UNICEF (2020), one third of rural houses lack improved water supplies,
130 while the ratio of rural settlements with improved sanitation facilities is still not clear.

131 In this framework, it should be noticed that the need of higher control on water-related and environmental
132 hazards is reported as a key challenge for safeguarding rural livelihoods (UNICEF, 2016). It is evident how
133 intense rainfall causes major floods and landslides in the country every year (*Mon et al.*, 2018), further
134 exacerbated by climate change (Herridge *et al.*, 2019). Literature shows that in other similar rural contexts
135 investing in erosion control and land management practices promoted the revitalization of marginal
136 territories and the transformation of rural livelihoods (Yurui *et al.*, 2019), and that on the other hand
137 landslides and severe soil erosion may hamper rural dwellers' well-being (Sudmeier-Rieux *et al.*, 2013).
138 Similar studies are absent for Myanmar, probably due to a lack of scientific analyses in rural areas.
139 However, the landslide- and erosion-rural livelihood nexus was made evident by the personal
140 communications given by the DRD officers involved in the participatory process.

141 **Methods**

142 ***Training course and selected topics***

143 Before undertaking the participatory selection of SLWM techniques and approaches, DRD officers were
144 trained with a course of around 60 hours on “Water Management and Disaster Risk Reduction”. The course
145 represented the second edition of an action developed by “GREAT - Management of Economic,
146 Environmental and Land Resources in the Municipalities of Magway and Natmawk” project. In 2019 the first
147 edition of the course was carried out within DRD, but with different participants. Based on the topics and

148 on the final evaluation of the first edition, a renewed list of topics was suggested to DRD administration by
149 the experts of Fondazione LINKS – Leading Innovation & Knowledge for Society and Università degli Studi di
150 Firenze (Italy) to be cross-checked and confirmed, with specific regards to the practical needs of DRD field
151 officers. After the feedback of DRD, the final program (Table 1) was confirmed.

152 The training lasted from 28/01/2020 to 07/02/2020 and was conducted by two Italian natural resources
153 management experts. To facilitate information sharing with DRD officers, the course was fully translated by
154 translators with expertise on GREAT project topics and objectives. An expert member of the central DRD
155 administration also helped the coordination between the project team and course attendants. A total of 45
156 DRD officers trained and actively contributed to the subsequent participatory process, being selected under
157 geographical and gender-equality criteria. The topics of the course, which also included practical training,
158 are presented in Table 1.

159 Table 1 – Topics selected for the training course undertaken before the participatory process

Lesson	Topics and main references
1	Driving forces, Pressures, State, Impacts and Responses (DPSIR) framework (European Environmental Agency, 1999); Ecosystem Services (Costanza <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
2	Introduction to sustainable water management; Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) (Global Water Partnership, 2018)
3	Overview of Climate Change in Myanmar (Kreft & Eckstein, 2014)
4	Sustainable groundwater development and management (IWMI, 2015); DRASTIC methodology (US Environmental Protection Agency, 1987)
5	Low cost supply methods for ground water development: Well protection and upgrading (Schneider, 2014); Low cost pumping systems (Bresci <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
6	Low cost supply methods for ground water development: Sand Dams (Maddrell & Neal, 2013; Villani <i>et al.</i> , 2018) and Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) (Dillon <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
7	Water Safety Plans (WSP) (Rondi <i>et al.</i> , 2015; WHO, 2006)
8	Low cost water and wastewater treatments (Collivignarelli <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
9	Low cost rainwater harvesting technologies (Mekdaschi Studer & Liniger, 2013; Thomas & Martinson, 2007)
10	Soil and water conservation techniques (Liniger <i>et al.</i> , 2007); Soil and water bioengineering (Petrone & Preti, 2010)
11	Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR, 2015)

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161 ***Participatory selection of best SLWM practices***

162 The participatory selection of best SLWM practices took place in the last two days of the course, in two
163 sessions of two hours each. To have a better geographic representation of the techniques to be considered,
164 participants were divided in 6 groups of almost equal numerosity, based on their region of provenance
165 (Figure 1).

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Figure 1 – Geographical localization of the groups created for the participatory process

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Participants were asked to indicate the practices already applied in their respective regions, and SLWM techniques that could be put in place or that can respond to actual needs in their geographic area. For these latter ones, DRD officers were asked to identify the first, second and third one in order of priority, and to indicate which techniques could be implemented in the short term. Participants were then asked to present their findings by the means of a poster, that was presented and discussed with all courses' attendants and with the authors of the present paper.

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Results and Discussion

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The practices selected with of the participatory process are presented in Figure 2. The process made evident both the most urgent actions to be put in place and those at a piloting stage. A detailed description is provided in the following sub-sections.

*note: Group 1 chose two, equal ranked, third priority options

181

182 Figure 2 - Participatory selection of best SLWM practices for rural water management in different areas of
 183 Myanmar

184 **Water Safety Plans and monitoring of water resources**

185 Water Safety Plans (WSP) represent community-based management strategies to ensure the safety of
 186 drinking water through the use of a risk assessment and management framework (WHO, 2006). Plans can
 187 be implemented with a six steps iterative methodology, including: 1) the engagement of the community
 188 and the creation of a “Water Safety Plan team”; 2) the description of the community water supply; 3) the

189 identification of risks, including hazardous events and actual hazard evaluation, and the assessment of the
190 existing control measures; 4) the development of an incremental improvement plan, including a detailed
191 description of the actions to be put in place, responsibilities and timing; 5) the monitoring of the
192 implemented measures and of the effectiveness of the plan; 6) the documentation and the revision of all
193 the aspects of the plan. WSP have been proven to represent flexible non-structural measures that can be
194 implemented both in rural (Rondi *et al.*, 2015) and in urban developed contexts (Sorlini *et al.*, 2017).
195 Application of WSP could be beneficial for rural water management in Myanmar representing both a way to
196 enhance rural water supply management, and to develop local-scale monitoring networks and
197 management committees. As a matter of fact, almost all groups indicated WSP as a priority measure that
198 can be implemented in the short term.

199 Regarding quality of basic water supply, groundwater, and in particular wells' water has to be monitored.
200 Some measures are in place, but the participatory workshop highlighted that commons guidelines and
201 procedure for wells registering and monitoring are needed and should be implemented in all rural contexts
202 of the country. The need is further justified, given the fact that the quality of groundwater supply for
203 drinking purposes is still uncertain in many regions (IWMI, 2015).

204 ***Sanitation and wastewater treatments***

205 To the best of our knowledge, accurate data regarding water sanitation systems in rural areas are lacking
206 for Myanmar. According to UNICEF (2016), despite a good coverage of basic sanitation systems, rural and
207 poorest households are facing some issues and may lack adequate sanitation systems. The urgency of
208 working on improved sanitation facilities emerged for groups 1 and 4, and in particular in the second one,
209 including Chin, Kachin and Rakhine States. It should be noted the group 4 includes the two poorest areas of
210 the country, since in Chin State almost six out of ten people are poor, while in Rakhine State about four out
211 of ten are poor (World Bank, 2019b). Here, it is evident a linkage between poverty conditions and the level
212 of water management in rural areas. It will therefore be crucial to invest in WASH planning for this latter
213 area.

214 ***Water harvesting***

215 Water harvesting techniques, namely techniques that allow “the process of concentrating precipitation
216 through runoff and storing it for beneficial use” (Oweis & Hachum, 2006), received great attention during
217 the participatory process. The main interest of DRD officers was for rooftop water harvesting systems
218 (Thomas & Martinson, 2007), sand dams (Maddrell & Neal, 2013) as well as small ponds (FAO, 2010).
219 Rooftop water harvesting was recognized as a key measure for securing water supply in rural areas.
220 According to the Myanmar IWRM study (van Meel *et al.*, 2014), in many rural areas rooftop water
221 harvesting, and water harvesting in general are almost the sole source of water. Despite this, integrated
222 country-scale plans for establishing common design and management guidelines seems to be lacking. DRD
223 officers' interest towards water harvesting technologies encompassed also larger scale solutions (sand
224 dams and ponds/small dams). Even though DRD officers are not responsible for irrigation management, in
225 some cases they follow the building of small civil infrastructures as the ones mentioned. While sand dams
226 have been seen as an innovative technology, it is needed to further train the technical DRD personnel on
227 their correct design and implementation. In addition to this, other studies referred to Myanmar as an
228 hotspot for potential increase of crop yields by water harvesting (Piemontese *et al.*, 2020).

229 ***Soil and water bioengineering***

230 Soil and water bioengineering is a civil engineering technique based on the use of live building material,
231 alone or integrated with standard materials for applications such as landslide/riverbank stabilization,
232 erosion control and road protection (Petroni & Preti, 2010; Rey *et al.*, 2019). It received some attention
233 during the participatory workshop as a mean of reducing erosion hazards and protect key infrastructures in
234 rural areas, such as streets, pipes, power and water treatment plans. Its potential was also highlighted as
235 control measure to be implemented in the development of rural WSP. Since soil and water bioengineering
236 represent a cost-effective approach if labor cost is low (Petroni & Preti, 2010), its application can be
237 appropriate for Myanmar rural contexts. Its application, however, will require adequate preliminary
238 studies, to check to what extent local tree and shrub species can represent adequate building materials
239 (Preti & Petrone, 2013).

240 ***Discussions and conclusions***

241 The present paper describes the findings of a participatory process undertaken involving Myanmar DRD
242 officers, in order to analyze and present SLWM practices to improve water and wastewater management in
243 rural areas of the country. These areas, that will be key for an equitable development of the country after
244 the end of the thirty-years military government, have so far received few attentions at the research level.

245 Key findings of the study were:

- 246 • WSP can represent a win-win measure to both improve the safety of rural water supply and to
247 establish a ground-level monitoring network to check the status of water supply systems in the
248 country. DRD has to be involved in their adoption, which should comply with WHO guidelines in
249 every regional state.
- 250 • Detailed analysis and a national monitoring system may be needed with reference to the quality of
251 groundwater sources, especially for wells. Well registering platforms should be extended to all rural
252 areas in the country, as well as long term groundwater quality monitoring.
- 253 • Information over the level of wastewater technologies present in rural areas should be gathered
254 and systematized, while special attention should be given to retrieve funding for improving these
255 infrastructures in poorest areas, and for awareness-raising on water quality-related issues among
256 rural communities.
- 257 • Water harvesting has the potential of supplying part of poor rural population with at least a stable
258 source of water for domestic uses. Its application, however, should be further implemented with a
259 national strategy.
- 260 • Soil and water bioengineering has the potential to be applied for erosion and landslide control
261 measure, but further assessment on its suitability in the country are needed. The application of this
262 latter technology may go beyond DRD's own task and will need to be planned also involving other
263 departments of MOALI.

264 Despite the limited timeframe (two-day workshop) and the link with the technologies presented in the
265 course, the present study represents a first structured attempt to highlight problems and potential
266 solutions related to water supply, wastewater management and water-related hazards in rural areas of
267 Myanmar. The present findings can represent an initial step for future water development project, both for
268 international cooperation agencies and for national initiatives. However, for any further initiative we also
269 recommend the full integration of forthcoming project efforts with actions and strategies already in put in
270 place by the Myanmar government, such as the Multi Sectoral National Plan for Nutrition (2017) and the
271 recent Rural Development Law.

272 Results also highlighted some evident nexus between rural poverty conditions and weak water systems
273 management, that should be further investigated to highlight the multiple interlinkages between water and
274 poverty in the country. Finally, the good participation of DRD staff and the outcomes of the process
275 demonstrated that the proposed methodology can provide meaningful information and could therefore be
276 upscaled and implemented in other contexts.

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